

PECTINASES IN MODERN BIOTECHNOLOGY: ITS INDUSTRIAL APPLICATIONS AND FUTURE HORIZONS

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ABSTRACT

The bioactive molecules known as enzymes control a wide range of chemical reactions in living tissues. Pectinases, the enzyme responsible for breaking down Pectin (Water-Soluble Carbohydrate present in plant cell walls and tissues), serve as an extensive enzyme for industrial use. Widely employed in industries such as textile processing, fruit juice clarification, pulp & paper industry, and waste treatment, these enzymes have gained prominence for their eco-friendly and energy-efficient catalytic properties. With advances in microbial biotechnology, the large-scale production of pectinases—particularly from fungi like *Aspergillus niger* and bacteria such as *Bacillus subtilis*—has become increasingly efficient through submerged and solid-state fermentation strategies. This review lays emphasis into the types, mechanisms, microbial sources, structural insights, and current industrial uses of pectinases such as sustainable bioprocessing, role in biorefineries, etc. It also highlights recent developments and emerging trends in recombinant enzyme technology and proposes future directions for research and commercial application.

Keywords: Biocatalysts, Microbial Enzymes, Industrial Biotechnology, Enzyme Engineering

1. Introduction

Pectinases, also known as pectinolytic enzymes, are a crucial class of enzymes that break down pectin, a complex heteropolysaccharide that is normally found in the primary cell walls and middle lamella of higher plants. These enzymes catalyse the hydrolysis, trans-elimination, or de-esterification of pectin, leading to its depolymerization. Given their efficacy, pectinases are now extensively utilized across diverse industries, including fruit juice clarification, textile processing, plant fiber degumming, and wastewater treatment (Jayani et al., 2005; Hoondal et al., 2002). Pectin is notably abundant in fruits and vegetables, where it plays a crucial structural role in maintaining tissue firmness and plant rigidity (Cosgrove, 1997). The enzymatic breakdown of this biopolymer by pectinases facilitates various industrial applications by enhancing product quality, increasing yields, and reducing environmental impacts. Compared to chemical methods, enzymatic processes offer advantages such as substrate specificity, lower energy consumption, and reduced production of harmful by-products, aligning well with sustainable and eco-friendly processing standards (Alkorta et al., 1998; Sharma et al., 2013).

Because of their ability to produce high-yield enzymes and their resistance to a variety of fermentation conditions, bacterial strains like *Bacillus subtilis* and fungal strains like

Aspergillus niger are popular microbiological sources of pectinases (Garg et al., 2016; Yu et al., 2017). These microorganisms produce a diversity of pectinolytic enzymes—pectin lyases (PLs), pectin methylesterases (PMEs) & polygalacturonases (PGs)—each with distinct action modes and industrial utility. Initially introduced in the early 20th century for clarifying fruit juices (Garg et al., 2016), pectinases have since emerged as critical tools in modern bioprocessing. Recent developments in protein engineering and recombinant DNA technology have produced more stable and efficient pectinase varieties appropriate for harsh industrial settings (Sharma et al., 2013). This review comprehensively explores the history, classification, sources, and structural mechanisms of pectinases, emphasizing their industrial relevance and highlighting future trends that could redefine enzymatic applications in green biotechnology.

2. History of Pectinase Research

The first step in creating pectinases was comprehending the structure of pectic compounds and how pectolytic enzymes break them down. Later, the microbial pectinase production came to light for several decades. The exploration of pectin-degrading enzymes dates back to the early 20th century when Kertesz (1930) first described microbial degradation of pectic substances during studies on fruit juice clarification. This marked the beginning of industrial application of pectinases, with early recognition of their potential in the food processing industry.

Over time, interest expanded beyond fruit clarification as researchers delved into the enzymatic breakdown of pectin and its role in plant tissue softening and microbial virulence. Early advances came from studies on fungi such as *Aspergillus niger*, which is still one of the most commonly used organisms because of its high extracellular enzyme yield and generally recognized as safe (GRAS) status, provided early advancements (Pariza & Foster, 1983). In the late 20th century, bacterial sources like *Erwinia chrysanthemi* and *Bacillus subtilis* became subjects of intensive research due to their ability to produce thermostable and alkaline pectinases, suitable for non-food industrial applications (Gummadi & Panda, 2003; Naidu & Panda, 1998).

More recently, advances in metagenomics and environmental screening have led to the discovery of novel pectinase-producing microbes from extreme environments. Strains like *Paenibacillus sp.*, *Streptomyces sp.*, and thermophilic *Geobacillus spp.* have demonstrated promising pectinolytic activity under harsh industrial conditions (Haile & Ayele, 2022; Ghaffar et al., 2022). Genomic and proteomic tools are now being used to engineer these enzymes for enhanced performance, such as improved thermostability and broad pH tolerance. Recombinant DNA (rDNA) technology has also facilitated the production of pectinase genes in heterologous hosts like *Escherichia coli* and *Pichia pastoris*, facilitating easier purification and modification (Patidar et al., 2021). These advancements are opening the door to more environmentally friendly and cost-effective production systems in the future.

3. Structure of Pectinases

The three-dimensional architectures of pectinases provide insights into the molecular foundation of enzyme function and the significance of individual amino acids within the active sites (Mayans et al., 1997; Jensen et al., 2010). These structural details elucidate the subtle distinctions in substrate specificity and catalytic performance among various pectinolytic enzymes. The first pectinase crystal structure to be solved was *Erwinia chrysanthemi* pectate lyase C (PelC) (Yoder et al., 1993), which showed a distinctive parallel β -helix fold. This same structure has since been observed in other pectate lyases including *Bacillus subtilis* Pel, PelA, PelE, and Pel9A (Pickersgill et al., 1994; Jenkins et al., 2001).

Pectinase enzymes typically have a complex structure that enables them to break down pectin. A common structural feature in many pectinases is the parallel β -helix, a right-handed cylindrical structure composed of parallel β -strands. With seven to nine helical turns, this parallel β -helix creates a prism-like shape that contributes to three parallel β -sheets (PB1, PB2, PB3). These sheets define the substrate-binding cleft, located between PB1 and surrounding loop regions. The cleft is essential for catalysis, where the substrate interacts and is cleaved. The detailed mechanisms of substrate binding and catalysis in this cleft have been studied using site-directed mutagenesis, molecular modelling, and X-ray crystallography, which have revealed critical insights into enzyme specificity and efficiency (Kita et al., 1996; Boz, 2021). The significance of particular residual amino acid present in the active site has been determined through recent research, highlighting their role in substrate recognition and the catalytic process. Furthermore, advancements in structural research have improved our comprehension of how pectinase enzymes are tailored for their industrial applications, including in food processing and biofuel production (Sánchez et al., 2022; Sun et al., 2023).

Figure 1 illustrates this structural diversity: (a) shows the structure of pectin lyase A from *Aspergillus aculeatus*, highlighting the β -helix architecture and substrate-binding groove; (b) displays the rhamnogalacturonan lyase from the same organism, which has a similar core fold but different surface loops, enabling it to recognize more complex pectin domains. These structural insights clarify how different enzymes from the same family adapt to specific substrates, underscoring their industrial and biological versatility.

Despite this progress, no representative structure for polymethylgalacturonase (PMG) has been solved to date (Sharma et al., 2013).

Fig. 1: *Aspergillus aculeatus* K 150a substrate complex's (a) Pectin Lyase A (PNLA) and (b) Rhamnogalacturonan Lyase (RG-Lyase) three-dimensional structure

4. Mode of Action of Pectinases

"Various microorganisms—including bacteria, actinomycetes, fungi, and yeasts—have been recognized for their ability to generate pectin-degrading enzymes, collectively referred to as microbial pectinases. Among these, extensively studied types include lyases, pectin esterases, polygalacturonases, and to some extent, proteases. Polygalacturonases (PGs), the most prevalent class of pectinases, act as catalysts in the hydrolysis of polygalacturonic acid chains by incorporating water molecules, as illustrated schematically in relevant literature (Alkorta et al., 1998). Another important enzyme, protopectinase, acts specifically on protopectin to convert it into soluble pectin. In contrast, lyases use a trans-elimination process to cleave the galacturonic acid polymer. In contrast, pectin esterases catalyse the breakdown of methyl ester bonds in the pectin backbone, leading to the release of methanol and other pectic compounds (Sharma et al., 2011). Pectinases play a crucial role in the fruit and vegetable processing industry, where they enhance juice extraction and improve clarity (Sharma et al., 2011). These enzymes are categorised based on how they affect the galacturonan backbone and mainly affect the pectic components of plant cell walls. Pectin depolymerases function by breaking glycosidic bonds between methyl-esterified galacturonic acid residues, whereas pectin methyl esterases remove methyl groups, converting high-methoxyl pectin into low-methoxyl pectin or pectic acid. Polygalacturonases cleave glycosidic bonds adjacent to unesterified carboxylic groups via hydrolysis, while pectate lyases utilize a β -elimination mechanism. Pectin lyases (PLs) and endo-polygalacturonases (endo-PGs) randomly break the pectin chain. In contrast, exo-pectin lyases generate unsaturated dimeric compounds from the reducing end, while exo-polygalacturonases cleave monomers or dimers from the non-reducing end. When pectin methyl esterases work in conjunction with polygalacturonases or endo-pectin lyases, they effectively degrade highly methylated pectin substrates (Sharma N. et al., 2013).

Fig. 2: The enzymatic action of PMGL, PMG, PGL, and PG on the pectin molecule. PMGL (polymethylgalacturonate lyase), PMG (polymethyl galacturonase), PGL (Pectinase Glycosyl Hydrolase), and PG (polygalacturonase) are the enzymes involved in pectin degradation. (Adapted from Garg et al., 2016)

5. Types of Pectinases

Pectin, a complex polysaccharide found in plant cell walls, is broken down by a class of enzymes known as pectinases. Based on how they function and the substrate they target, these enzymes are divided into a number of types. Pectinesterases (PE), also known as pectinmethyl hydrolases, primarily target the methyl ester group of galacturonate units, facilitating the de-esterification of pectin's methoxyl group to yield pectic acid (Cosgrove, 1997). Polygalacturonases (PGs) degrade polygalacturonic acid, causing the cleavage of glycosidic linkages and depolymerizing pectin (Cosgrove, 1997). Pectin lyases (PLs) break down the 1,4-glycosidic bonds connecting galacturonic acid units, producing unsaturated oligogalacturonides, which are commonly used in industries like fruit juice production for enhancing extraction and clarifying processes (Schols & Voragen, 1996). Rhamnogalacturonases (RGase) specifically hydrolyse the α -1,4-glycosidic linkage between rhamnose and galacturonic acid in pectin, releasing smaller pectin fragments (Schols & Voragen, 1996). Pectinases are further divided into three groups according to how they function: endo-liquefying or depolymerizing enzymes, such as endo-polygalacturonases (endo-PGs) and endo-pectate lyases (endo-PLs), which break down internal glycosidic linkages randomly through hydrolysis (Tapre & Jain, 2014); exo- or saccharifying enzymes, including exo-polygalacturonases (exo-PGs) and exo-pectate lyases (exo-PLs), which react on non-reducing ends to gradually release monomeric units (Tapre & Jain, 2014); and trans-eliminating enzymes, such as pectin lyases (PLs) and certain pectate lyases (PLs), which produce unsaturated oligogalacturonides through a trans-elimination process, distinct from hydrolysis (Tapre & Jain, 2014). These enzymes are crucial in various industrial applications, including food processing, where they aid in juice extraction, clarification, and other processes that require the breakdown of pectin (Sánchez et al., 2022; Boz, 2021).

Fig. 3: Types of pectinases (created using MS Word)

6. Microbial Sources of Pectinases

Various kinds of animals, including bacteria, fungus, yeasts, insects, nematodes, protozoa, and plants produce pectinolytic enzymes naturally (Garg et al., 2016). The most typical food source for microorganisms that produce pectinase is decomposing plant matter, which is produced in large quantities by saprophytic fungi (Gummadi et al., 2003). Multiple studies on microbial enzymes have highlighted the development of various pectinase forms, each exhibiting distinct molecular masses and kinetic properties. Below mentioned (Table 1.) is the list of some of the microbial sources of pectinases and their source of isolation.

Table 1. Some microbial sources of Pectinases

S.no.	Sources	Microbial Isolates	References
<i>Bacteria</i>			
1.	Agro-waste	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	Torimiro & Okonji, 2013
2.	Soil	<i>Bacillus sp. (ZGL14)</i>	Yu et al., 2017
3.	National center for agricultural utilization research (USA)	<i>Bacillus pumilus</i>	Tepe et al., 2014
4.	Market solid waste	<i>Bacillus cereus</i>	Namasivayam et al., 2011
5.	Hot spring	<i>Bacillus halodurans (M29)</i>	Mei et al., 2013

6.	Soil sample	<i>Bacillus mojavenensis 14</i>	Ghazala et al., 2015
7.	Pig intestine	<i>Lachnospira pectinoschiza</i>	Cornick et al., 1994
8.	Soil	<i>Pseudomonas solanacearum</i>	Schell et al., 1994
9.	Algerian raw milk	<i>Lactobacillus lactis subsp. cremoris</i>	Karam et al., 1995
10.	<i>Saintpaulia ionantha</i>	<i>E. chrysanthemi 3604</i>	Laurent et al., 2000
11.	Industrial wastewater	<i>Paenibacillus polymyxa</i>	Khan et al., 2022
12.	Soil from compost yard	<i>Geobacillus thermodenitrificans</i>	Ghaffar et al., 2022
13.	Fermented soybean	<i>Bacillus velezensis</i>	Sharma et al., 2023

Fungi			
1.	Rotten lemons	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	Maldonado et al., 1994
2.	Brazilian soil samples	<i>Penicillium sp.</i>	Jayani et al., 2005
3.	Fruit market	<i>Rhizomucor sp.</i>	Siddiqui et al., 2013
4.	Soil	<i>Rhizopus sp.</i>	Jayani et al., 2005
5.	Agrowaste samples	<i>Trichoderma sp.</i>	Okafor et al., 2010
6.	Champagne wines	<i>Saccharomyces cerevisiae</i>	Gainvors et al., 1994
7.	The DSM collection and the Institut für Gärungsgewerbe und Biotechnologie in Berlin	<i>Candida sp.</i>	Call et al., 1984
8.	Professor Sidney Crow, Department of Biology, Georgia State University, Georgia, USA	<i>Pichia sp.</i>	Moharib et al., 2000
9.	Patagonian lake Toncek	<i>Rhodotorula sp.</i>	Libkind et al., 2004
10.	Infected vegetable	<i>Aureo basidium sp.</i>	Parini et al., 1988
11.	Agricultural waste (banana peel)	<i>Aspergillus tubingensis</i>	Yadav et al., 2021

12.	Rotten pineapple	<i>Penicillium citrinum</i>	Bhatti et al., 2020
13.	Grape pomace	<i>Trichoderma viride</i>	Singh et al., 2019

Plants			
1.	Malaysian Agricultural Research and Development Institute (MARDI), Serdang	<i>Carica papaya</i>	Fayyaz et al., 1995; Innocenzo et al., 2001
2.	Various Plants	<i>Lycopersicum esculentum</i>	Warrilow et al., 1994
3.	Local supermarkets	<i>Prunus malus</i>	Macdonald and Evans, 1996
4.	Citrus world, lake Wales, FL	<i>Vitis vinifera</i>	Corredig et al., 2000
5.	Valencia	<i>Citrus sp.</i>	Arias and Burns, 2002
6.	Plantation in Coatlán del Rio	<i>Pouteria sapota</i>	Arenas-Ocampo et al., 2003
7.	Several trees	<i>Maliphigia glabra L.</i>	Assis et al., 2004
8.	Wild fig	<i>Ficus carica</i>	Ahmed et al., 2020
9.	Guava	<i>Psidium guajava</i>	Rani et al., 2021
Yeast			
1.	Apple pomace	<i>Pichia kudriavzevii</i>	Tsegaye et al., 2021

7. Applications of Pectinases

According to Kertesz's early report from 1930, pectinases were first used commercially to clarify apple juice. Since then, their role has expanded significantly, and today, pectinases are indispensable in various traditional and emerging industrial processes. Their effectiveness has been established across various applications, including plant fiber processing, textile production, tea and coffee fermentation, oil extraction, wastewater treatment, and even virus purification (Jayani et al., 2005; Garg et al., 2016). In the last few years, the application of microbial pectinases has expanded to include sustainable bioprocessing, such as enzymatic retting and eco-friendly bio-scouring in the textile sector (Sharma et al., 2023). Their use in fruit juice clarification and pulp treatment continues to evolve, with modern enzyme blends tailored for specific fruits and pH conditions,

improving yield and processing time (Haile & Ayele, 2022). Furthermore, current research emphasizes their integration in circular bioeconomy models, where agro-industrial waste can serve as both a substrate and a pectinase production medium (Singh et al., 2021). These enzymes are also being explored for their role in novel biotechnological systems, such as biorefineries and smart enzyme formulations, for enhanced productivity and reduced environmental impact (Ghaffar et al., 2022).

7.1. Fruit Juice Extraction

The most prevalent industrial use of pectinases involves the extraction and purification of fruit juices. To make fruit juices clearer, a combination of pectinases and amylases is utilized, reducing filtration time by 50% (Blanco et al., 1999). Modern formulations of pectinolytic enzymes are tailored to specific fruit matrices, enhancing yield and maintaining nutritional quality (Ortiz et al., 2017; Haile & Ayele, 2022). Pectin methylesterase and calcium infusion in citrus fruits have been shown to enhance texture and firmness during processing, offering commercial advantages in canned or pickled products (Baker & Wicker, 1996; Mehanni et al., 2017).

7.2. Bio-Scouring of Cotton Fibres & Textile Processing

Within the textile industry sector, pectinases have replaced caustic soda for bioscouring—a pre-treatment process that removes pectin, waxes, and non-cellulosic impurities from cotton. This eco-friendly enzymatic method reduces pollution, water use, and energy consumption compared to traditional alkaline treatments (Hoondal et al., 2000). Recent research has optimized microbial pectinase blends for better fabric softness and dyeability while preserving fiber integrity (Sharma et al., 2023; Patidar et al., 2021).

7.3. Degumming of Plant Bast Fibres

Outside of the xylem, phloem, or pericycle, the soft, flexible fibres called bast fibres, form in clusters. Bast fibres include Sun hemp and Ramie. Before the fibres are used to make textiles, the gum inside of them needs to be removed. The chemical degumming procedure is poisonous, non-biodegradable, and polluting. For the aforementioned issue, biotechnological degumming with pectinases and xylanases offers a cost-effective and environmentally beneficial solution (Kapoor et al., 2001). Recent advances have demonstrated the scalability of this process using solid-state fermentation techniques (Almeida et al., 2023).

7.4. Retting of Plant Fibres

Retting is the process of separating bast fibres from the woody core by removing pectic substances. Pectinase-mediated retting provides a controlled and faster alternative to traditional microbial retting, which is slow and environmentally challenging. Enzymatic retting has shown to improve fiber fineness, reduce microbial contamination, and shorten processing time (Hoondal et al., 2002; Sharma et al., 2023). This approach is particularly profitable to flax, jute, and hemp processing industries seeking greener solutions. This method is being increasingly adopted by sustainable textile producers worldwide.

7.5. Tea & Coffee Fermentation

During coffee processing, pectinases are used to remove the mucilage layer that coats the beans of coffee, a crucial step in the wet fermentation process. Enzymatic treatment accelerates this mucilage breakdown, ensuring uniform fermentation and enhancing bean quality (Carr, 1985). Similarly, in tea production, pectinases help in reducing foam-forming components in instant tea powders by degrading pectins. This results in improved solubility and clarity of tea extracts, especially in ready-to-drink products. More recently, fungal-derived pectinases have been employed in specialty tea and coffee production due to their enhanced activity at varied temperatures and pH levels (Bhatti et al., 2020; Ghaffar et al., 2022).

7.6. Paper Pulp Industry

In the paper pulp industry, pectinases help in the removal of pectic substances that interfere with fiber bonding and water drainage. Pectins increase the cationic demand and reduce paper strength by binding with metal ions and retention aids. Pectinases such as polygalacturonases and pectate lyases depolymerize polygalacturonic acid chains, thereby reducing the cationic demand and improving the performance of retention agents (Reid & Ricard, 2000). This enzymatic treatment enhances water removal during papermaking and reduces the need for chemical additives, making the process more eco-efficient (Viikari et al., 2001). Novel applications include their use in peroxide bleaching processes for improved pulp brightness and lower chemical usage (Nguyen et al., 2020; Viikari et al., 2001).

7.7. Plant Viruses Purification

Pectinases aid in the isolation of virus particles trapped within pectin-rich plant tissues in plant virology. When used alongside cellulases, these enzymes facilitate the gentle maceration of tissue, yielding high-purity viral preparations ideal for vaccine development and diagnostics (Salazar & Jayasinghe, 1999; Nguyen et al., 2020).

7.8. Wastewater Treatment

Pectin-rich wastewater from citrus processing and vegetable canning industries presents significant challenges for conventional treatment systems due to the resistance of pectic substances to microbial degradation. These substances increase chemical oxygen demand (COD) and reduce treatment efficiency. Pectinases, especially alkaline endopectate lyases produced by alkalophilic *Bacillus* species, are used to pretreat this wastewater by degrading the pectic polysaccharides into simpler, biodegradable compounds (Tanabe et al., 1987). This enzymatic pretreatment significantly enhances the performance of downstream

biological processes, such as activated sludge systems, by reducing the organic load and improving microbial assimilation. Studies have also shown that this method reduces sludge volume and accelerates processing time (Hoondal et al., 2002). Traditional chemical treatments, which are frequently expensive and harmful to the environment, can be replaced with an environmentally friendly enzymatic method. More recent approaches utilize engineered microbial consortia and enzyme cocktails to improve treatment efficacy in agro-industrial wastewater systems (Singh et al., 2021).

7.9. Oil Extraction

In the extraction of edible oils from fruits like olives, dates, and flaxseed, pectinases play a key role in breaking down cell wall polysaccharides, facilitating the release of intracellular oils. Enzymatic oil extraction leads to higher yields, reduced extraction time, and improved oil quality with lower peroxide and free fatty acid content (Mehanni et al., 2017; Ortiz et al., 2017). Compared to conventional solvent extraction, enzymatic methods are safer and environmentally friendly. Current studies are optimizing process parameters using statistical tools and machine learning to maximize enzymatic oil extraction efficiency (Almeida et al., 2023).

7.10. Enhancement of Red Wines' Chromaticity and Stability

Pectinases are added during red wine production to degrade pectin in grape skins, which facilitates the release of anthocyanins and tannins—key compounds responsible for color, aroma, and mouthfeel. Enzymatic maceration improves wine color intensity, turbidity reduction, and filterability (Revilla & González-San José, 2003). Wines treated with pectinolytic enzymes also show better long-term stability and sensory quality compared to untreated controls. Their role in stabilizing color compounds during aging is being further optimized using recombinant enzymes with higher activity at wine fermentation conditions (Ghaffar et al., 2022).

7.11. Paper Making

Pectinases have found valuable application in the paper industry, particularly in addressing the challenges posed by pectic substances during the paper-making process. Paper production involves forming sheets from a suspension of fibres, fines, and fillers such as clay and calcium carbonate. Effective drainage is essential, and this process relies on retention aids—usually cationic polymers—to prevent the loss of fine particles through the filter fabrics (Horn & Linhart, 1996). However, bleaching with alkaline peroxide releases pectins and polygalacturonic acids, which interfere with these retention systems due to their high cationic demand (Holmbom, 1991). The degree of polymerization influences this demand: long-chain polygalacturonates interact more strongly with cationic agents, whereas shorter fragments have negligible effects (Thornton et al., 1994). Pectinases depolymerize these acidic polysaccharides, thereby reducing cationic demand and improving both retention and drainage efficiency (Reid & Ricard, 2000). In addition to improving pulp

quality, this enzymatic method makes the process of producing paper more economical and environmentally friendly.

8. Conclusion

Pectinases enhance both yield and quality in various industrial processes and are recognized as essential enzymes within the sector. Ongoing research continues to unveil novel applications for pectinases, which have become crucial biocatalysts across diverse industries due to their specificity, eco-friendly nature, and operational efficiency. Their use has notably improved yield, product quality, and sustainability in processes ranging from juice clarification and fiber retting to oil extraction and textile processing. Looking forward, the future of pectinases lies in harnessing advanced protein engineering and recombinant DNA technologies to develop more robust and substrate-specific enzyme variants. Genetically modified microbial hosts such as *Pichia pastoris* and *Escherichia coli* are increasingly being explored for heterologous expression of engineered pectinase genes to enhance stability and reduce production costs (Patidar et al., 2021; Haile & Ayele, 2022).

Pectinases' incorporation into biorefinery models—particularly in lignocellulosic biomass valorisation—holds promise for more sustainable production of biofuels, organic acids, and bioplastics. Moreover, their potential use in biomedical applications, including targeted drug delivery and cancer therapy, is gaining attention due to their ability to degrade extracellular matrices (Nguyen et al., 2020). With the advancement of computational tools, artificial intelligence (AI), and machine learning, enzyme modelling and directed evolution are being significantly accelerated, offering new avenues for the design of tailor-made pectinases with desirable industrial traits (Almeida et al., 2023). Continued exploration of microbial diversity, coupled with omics technologies, will further expand the enzyme repertoire available for industrial bioprocessing. With increasing demand for greener technologies, pectinases are poised to become a cornerstone of sustainable and intelligent biomanufacturing.

9. References

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